

EFFECT OF MODULAR LEARNING ON PERFORMANCE IN BIOLOGY, CHEMISTRY AND PHYSICS OF GENERAL SCIENCE STUDENTS OF MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to find out what are the effects of modular learning to the performance in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101 among 2nd year General Science students. Moreover, it determined what are the performance level of General Science students in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101. Lastly, it explored if there are significant difference of the effect of modular learning and the level of performance in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101 of the 2nd year General Science students. The study used the descriptive quantitative research design where the researcher utilized a checklist questionnaire to acquire the data needed. The data was gathered in Mindanao State University-Sulu campus. The respondents of the study were thirty (30) students which are the 2nd year general science student of the College of Education. Purposive Sampling was used in the selection of the respondents. The statistical tools used in this study were weighted mean and t-test. Finally, base from the research findings, the researchers concluded that modular learning is an effective alternative modality in learning among 2nd year General science students. However, effects of modular learning were not related with the level of performance of the students.

Keywords: *modular learning, academic performance, biology, chemistry, physics*

INTRODUCTION

Learning is the soul of education that eliminates ignorance within individual's mind, it is an ability possessed by human being that plays a crucial role in the existence of human life, from the moment a person was brought into this world, the process of learning begins until he or she reaches the stage of late adulthood which means that learning is a continuous process. According to Ambrose (2020), "learning is a process that leads to change, which occurs as a result of experience and increases the potential of improved performance and future learning".

Meanwhile, learner is a term used for individuals that acquire a certain knowledge and is commonly used in school as it refers to the student. They are the one that seeks knowledge through experiences that they have acquired from the teacher's lessons and school activities given to them during school hours. That is how the student engaged in the process of learning. But in the year of 2019, when everyone was experiencing difficulties in the sudden adjustment to the new normal way of living because of the pandemic (Covid19), the process of learning of student changed and have to make an adjustment in order to still pursue education despite of pandemic and that leads to the use of modular set of learning, where the student must practice a self-study inside their home to prevent the spread of virus.

Jailani, et al (2024), By this time, maybe the pandemic is gone but we cannot deny that its trace still remains thus education must not stop. In order to continue the learning of the youths, the government has come up with a solution to render the needs of the students because we all believe that education is the key to success so it must not be disrupted. The idea of continuing education has been on the line since it is one of the priorities of the government; the learnings of the students. Abdurahman, et al (2024) This scenario also holds true in MBHTE-Sulu in the Bangsamoro Region in Muslim Mindanao, Southern Philippines where teachers in the intermediate grade level have also facing several challenges in the mainstream of classroom instruction. It is very hard for teachers to facilitate learning in the classroom considering the in-depth contents of science, the classroom strategies and materials to be used, more so, the way how students being evaluated in the light of the k-12 curriculum.

In this situation, where every student has to practice their self to learn their lessons all by themselves there might be some factors that may affect their academic performance toward a certain course due to the lack of physical presence of their instructors. However, there are also student who are not totally struggling to practice self-study as they are used to it or they might just have a higher IQ level than the other student. Since there are three categories of IQ level which are the Gifted, Above Average Intelligence and the Average Intelligence. The researchers seek to find the solution for this study for the purpose of determining the effect of modular learning on the level of performance among the students taking up the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Sciences. The researchers believe that this research will contribute to the improvement of academic performance of the students who has a plan of entering and are currently taking the course of BSED General Sciences. Additionally, it is useful on the part of teachers as they can relate to students' current situation and their needs in acquiring the best quality

education.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of modular learning on the performance in biology, chemistry and physics among students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science in Mindanao State University-Sulu. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What are the effects of modular learning on the performance in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101 among students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu?
2. What are the performance levels of General Science students in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101?
3. Is there significant difference of the effect of modular learning and the level of performance in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The setting of the study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu. The Mindanao State University-Sulu is the only university in Jolo, Sulu located at Capitol Site near the Provincial Capitol. The said university is composed of seven (7) colleges excluding the Mindanao State University-Sulu Laboratory High School. Particularly, this study is conducted at College of Education in between the College of Business Administration and College of Public Affairs.

Sampling Method

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study.

Moreover, the respondents of this study are the Second Year General Science Students of the College of Education in Mindanao State University-Sulu which is comprised of thirty (30) students.

Research Instrument

The researchers used questionnaire checklist to obtain the needed information for this study and to help them answer the objectives of the study in finding out the effect of Modular Learning to their academic Performance in Chemistry 032, Physics 101 and Biology 021. Below is the attached scale used for the performance of the students.

Table 3.1
SCALE USED FOR THE PERFORMANCE OF THE STUDENTS

Scales	Grades	
Description		
4	1.25-1.5	Very Satisfactory
3	1.75-2.0	Satisfactory
2	2.25-2.5	Good
1	2.75-3.0	Fair

Statistical Treatment of Data

For the analysis of data, the researchers used Weighted Mean as a statistical tool in dealing with the effect of Modular learning in the performance of General Science students and for the significant difference of the effect of Modular learning on the level of performance in Biology, Chemistry and Physics used T-test.

Scope and Delimitation

The main purpose of this study is to provide an accurate information regarding the effect of modular learning on the level of performance among General Science Students of the College of Education of Mindanao State University Sulu. The researcher limited the study to 30 second year students taking up Bachelor of Secondary Education major in General Sciences of Mindanao State University Sulu, College Year 2020-2021. Each of the respondent were given a questionnaire to answer that serves as survey.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the result, discussion and analysis of the data gathered by the researchers. This includes the effect of modular learning to the performance in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101 among the students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021 and Performance Levels of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science students in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101 in the School Year 2020-2021 and of course the significant difference of the effects of modular learning and the level of performance in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101 among students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021.

Table 4.1A
Effect of Modular Learning in Biology 021

ITEMS	Mean	Description
1. Modular learning improves my reading comprehension in Biology.	2.80	Effective
2. Modular Learning boosted my self-confidence dealing biology by answering my paper works independently.	2.87	Effective
3. Modular learning motivates me to gain a better performance in Biology	2.53	Effective
4. Modular learning enriches my vocabulary in scientific term used in Biology	2.77	Effective
5. Modular learning makes biology more interesting to learn.	2.77	Effective
6. Modular learning lessens the difficulties in understanding the topics in Biology.	2.40	Less Effective
7. Modular learning improved my performance in Biology.	2.50	Effective
OVERALL MEAN	2.66	Effective

Legend: 1.00-1.49= Not Effective, 1.5-2.49 =Less Effective, 2.5-3.49= Effective, 3.5-4.49= Very Effective

Table 4.1A presents the effect of modular learning in Biology 021 among the students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021. As shown in the table, the mean of the responses to the following statements; *Modular Learning improves my reading comprehension in Biology 021 (Item No. 1)*, *Modular Learning boosted my self-confidence dealing Biology 021 (Item No. 2)* *Modular learning motivates me to gain a better performance in Biology 021 (Item No. 3)*, *Modular Learning enriches my vocabulary in scientific term used in Biology 021 (Item No. 4)* *Modular learning makes Biology 021 more interesting to learn (Item No. 5)* and *Modular learning improved my performance in Biology 021 (Item No. 7)* with the mean of 2.80, 2.87, 2.53, 2.77, 2.77, 2.53 respectively, given descriptive equivalent of “**Effective**”.

Nevertheless, the mean of the responses to the statement; *Modular Learning lessens the difficulties in understanding the topics in Biology 021 (Item No. 6)* with a descriptive equivalent of “**Less Effective**”.

The data shows that the overall mean is **2.66** with a descriptive equivalent of “**Effective**”. This means that, the data implies that Modular Learning has a positive effect on the performance in Biology 021, among the students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021.

Table 4.1B
Effect of Modular Learning in Chemistry 032

ITEMS	Mean	Description
1. Modular learning improves my reading comprehension in Chemistry.	2.70	Effective
2. Modular Learning boosted my self-confidence dealing chemistry by answering my paper works independently	2.60	Effective
3. Modular learning motivates me to gain a better performance in Chemistry.	2.60	Effective
4. Modular learning enriches my vocabulary in scientific term used in Chemistry	2.70	Effective
5. Modular learning makes chemistry more interesting to learn.	2.67	Effective
6. Modular learning lessens the difficulties in understanding the topics in Chemistry.	2.33	Less Effective
7. Modular learning improved my performance in Chemistry	2.50	Effective
OVERALL MEAN	2.59	Effective

Legend: 1.00-1.49= Not Effective, 1.5-2.49 =Less Effective, 2.5-3.49= Effective, 3.5-4.49= Very Effective

Table 4.1B presents the effect of modular learning in Chemistry 032 among the students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021.

As shown in the table, the mean of the responses to the following statements; *Modular Learning improves my reading comprehension in Chemistry 032 (Item No. 1) Modular Learning boosted my self-confidence dealing Chemistry 032 by answering my paper works independently (Item No.2) Modular learning motivates me to gain a better performance in Chemistry 032 (Item No. 3) Modular Learning enriches my vocabulary in scientific term used in Chemistry 032 (Item No. 4) Modular learning makes and*

Chemistry 032 more interesting to learn (**Item No.5**) and Modular learning improved my performance in Chemistry 032 (**Item No. 7**) with the mean of 2.70, 2.60, 2.60, 2.70, 2.67, 2.50 respectively given the descriptive equivalent of “**Effective**”.

Nevertheless, the mean of the responses to the statement that *Modular Learning lessens the difficulties in understanding the topics in Chemistry 032* (**Item No. 6**) with the mean of 2.33 given the descriptive equivalent of “**Less Effective**”.

The data shows that the overall mean is **2.59** given the descriptive equivalent of “**Effective**”. This means that, the data implies that Modular Learning has a positive effect on the performance in Chemistry 032 among the students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021.

Table 4.1C
Effect of Modular Learning in Physics 101

ITEMS	Mean	Description
1. Modular learning improves my reading comprehension in Physics	2.60	Effective
2. Modular Learning boosted my self-confidence dealing physics by answering my paper works independently	2.43	Less Effective
3. Modular learning motivates me to gain a better performance in Physics.	2.53	Effective
4. Modular learning enriches my vocabulary in scientific term used in Physics	2.53	Effective
5. Modular learning makes physics more interesting to learn.	2.46	Less Effective
6. Modular learning lessens the difficulties in understanding the topics in Physics.	2.40	Less Effective
7. Modular learning improved my performance in Physics.	2.43	Less Effective
OVERALL MEAN	2.49	Less Effective

Legend: 1.00-1.49= Not Effective, 1.5-2.49 =Less Effective, 2.5-3.49= Effective, 3.5-4.49= Very Effective

Table 4.1C presents the effect of modular learning to the performance in Physics 101 among the students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General

Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021. As shown in the table, the mean of the responses to the following statements; *Modular Learning improves my reading comprehension in Physics 101 (Item No. 1)* *Modular learning motivates me to gain a better performance in Physics 101 (Item No. 3)* *Modular Learning enriches my vocabulary in scientific term used in Physics 101 (Item No.4)* 2.60, 2.53, 2.53 respectively given the descriptive equivalent of “**Effective**”.

Nevertheless, the mean of the responses to following statements; *Modular Learning boosted my self-confidence dealing Physics 101 by answering my paper works independently (Item No. 2)* *Modular learning makes Physics 101 more interesting to learn (Item No. 5)* *Modular Learning lessens the difficulties in understanding the topics in Physics 101 (Item No. 6)* and lastly *Modular learning improved my performance in Physics 101 (Item No. 7)* 2.43, 2.46, 2.40, 2.43 respectively given the descriptive equivalent of “**Less Effective**”.

The data shows that the overall mean is **2.49** with a descriptive equivalent of “**Less Effective**”. This means that, the data implies that Modular Learning has a less effect on the performance in Physics 101 among students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021.

Table 4.1D
Effect of Modular Learning in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101

Performance in	Mean	Description
BIOLOGY 021	2.66	Effective
CHEMISTRY 032	2.59	Effective
PHYSICS 101	2.49	Less Effective
OVERALL MEAN	2.58	Effective

Legend: 1.00-1.49= Not Effective, 1.5-2.49 =Less Effective, 2.5-3.49= Effective, 3.5-4.49= Very Effective

Table 4.1D presents the effect of modular learning among the students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021. The effect of modular learning in biology 021 with the mean of **2.66** given descriptive equivalent of “**Effective**”. In Chemistry 032 with the mean of **2.59** given descriptive equivalent of “**Effective**”. In Physics 101, mean is **2.49** with a descriptive

equivalent of “**Less Effective**”.

However as shown in the table, the overall mean in the three mentioned subjects is **2.58** with a descriptive equivalent of “**Effective**”. This means that, the data implies that Modular Learning effective among the students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021.

Lim (2016), this study entitled “Effectiveness of Modular Instruction in Word Problem Solving of BEED Students”, used Quasi-experimental design to the third year BEED students. Based on the findings cited, it concluded that modular instruction in teaching Math specifically word problem solving, it is effective teaching approach.

According to Dr. Padmapriya P.V. (2015), modules helped to develop self-learning capacity among the learners. The present study implied that this is self-learning style in which immediate reflection of the self is possible, which motivated the students to regulate and manage their own learning styles, and thereby to create an interest and attitude towards science among the students as they are free to learn at their own pace. With the help of modules students learned and interacted which boost their confidence in their own learning. The student’s treated with modular approach achieved higher mean scores than students teach through activity-oriented method. The study revealed that effectiveness of self-instructional module on achievement among secondary school students and the administrators must take necessary steps to give special training to teacher in developing modular packages.

Table 4.2
Performance levels in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101

Items	Total Average	Description
Biology 021	2.93	Satisfactory
Chemistry 032	3.40	Satisfactory
Physics 101.	3.10	Satisfactory
OVERALL MEAN	3.14	SATISFACTORY

Legend: 1.00-1.49= Fair 1.5-2.49 =Good 2.5-3.49= Satisfactory 3.5-4.00= Very Satisfactory

Table 4.2 Presents the Performance Levels of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science Students in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101 in the School Year 2020-2021. As shown in the table the data shows that Biology 021 gathered the mean of **2.93** with a descriptive equivalent of **“Satisfactory”** as well as in Chemistry 032 gathered the mean of **3.40** with a descriptive equivalent of **“Satisfactory”** and also, in Physics 101 gathered the mean of **3.10** with a descriptive equivalent of **“Satisfactory”** and so their overall mean is **3.14** with a description of **“Satisfactory”**.

According to Victorio B. Duyan (n.d.) in his study entitled " Effectiveness of Modular Approach in Teaching and Learning on Chemistry of GASES and their Application at University of Perpetual Help System Laguna (UPHSL)", modular approach should be applied to other subjects as well as other level of education and teachers would use modular teaching to improve the academic achievements of the students. And so, in 2020-2021 the students of BSED got the satisfactory level of performance because it only proves the effectiveness of modular learning.

Table 4.3
Significant difference of the effect of modular learning and the level of performance in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101

ITEMS	T	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
EFFECT MODULAR LEARNING AND THE LEVEL OF PERFORMANCE	10.035	.000	Ho Rejected

Table 4.3: Presents the significant difference of the effect of modular learning and the level of performance in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101 among the students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science of MSU Sulu, School Year 2020-2021. The data revealed that the sig. value is .000 which is lesser than 0.05 the significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected meaning “There is significant difference of the effect of Modular learning and the level of performance”.

According to Anthony Abaidoo (2018) as cited in Narah and Abdullah (2016), academic performance is the knowledge gained which is assessed by marks by a teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time and they added that these goals are measured by using continuous assessment or examinations results.

According to Shuja, Qureshi, Schaeffer, & Zareen (2019) in their study entitled

“Effect of m-learning on student's academic performance mediated by facilitation discourse and flexibility”, as they suggested that a multifaceted phenomenon, influenced by diverse factors such as meta-reflective learning and cognition, interest, motivation for learning, skills, engagement, quality of teaching and socio-economic status, characterized by enhance student’s capability to perform at the desired level. Don Elger (n.d.) claimed performance, as the adage goes, is a “journey not a destination.” The location in the journey is labeled as the level of performance. Each level characterizes the effectiveness or quality of a performance.

Conclusions

On the basis of the foregoing findings, the following conclusion were drawn; Findings are limited by the used of checklist questionnaire in the criteria of the effect of modular learning in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101 assessed as “**effective**” The level of performance in Biology 021, Chemistry 032 and Physics 101 among the students of Bachelor of secondary major in general science assessed as “**Satisfactory**”. The effect of modular learning and the level of performance among the students of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science were not related, in fact there is significant difference of the effect of modular learning and the level of performance of the General Science students. Base from the research findings the researchers concludes that modular learning is an effective alternative to use in dealing with the continuous learning of the students even at their own home. However, Effects of modular learning were not related with the level of performance of the students. The students might find the modular learning as a very challenging task as they are learning on their own. But their determination to learn more and to maintain their level of performance as satisfactory made them to strive hard to put an additional effort in learning their lesson continuously and independently which made the majority of them to gain a satisfactory level of performance is what matters most.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings, the researchers hereby formulate the following recommendations;

1. The administrators should continue in supporting and motivating the teacher’s way of imparting their knowledge through giving them the essential materials in making modules like bond papers, printers and inks to ensure good quality education.
2. The teacher must continue in performing their task as an educator effectively even they do not often meet their students like how they use to be because of the threat of Covid-19 virus. In order to still promote a good quality education. For instance, in chemistry and physics the teacher might do something that adds up with their explanation in modules through making video explanation regarding their topic specially in solving situational problems and if possible they could explain the topic in the vernacular language, in order for the students to learn the lesson more effectively and whole heartedly.

3. Future researchers should investigate the same studies in order to prove more the accuracy of the findings of this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers hereby declare that an informed consent was obtained from the respondents of the study. In addition, the researchers assure that the information gathered from respondents are kept confidential. Plagiarism was strictly observed throughout the research process, and that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research purposes.

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